

KEEPING UP THE PUPILS MOTIVATED WHEN TEACHING VOCABULARY

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Annotation. *The article is about the use of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching foreign languages, their advantages and positive effect in developing student's communicative competence. It shares with some non-traditional forms of conducting lessons which provide an opportunity to develop the creative independence of students, to teach them to work with various sources of knowledge.*

Key words: *communicative competence, pedagogical technologies. Non-traditional methods, teaching process, intercultural communication of English language.*

ПОДДЕРЖАНИЕ МОТИВАЦИИ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ЛЕКСИКИ

Аннотация. *В статье речь идет об использовании современных педагогических технологий в обучении иностранным языкам, их преимуществах и положительном влиянии на развитие коммуникативной компетентности учащихся. Он перекликается с некоторыми нетрадиционными формами проведения уроков, которые дают возможность развивать творческую самостоятельность учащихся, учить их работать с различными источниками знаний.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникативная компетентность, педагогические технологии. Нетрадиционные методы, учебный процесс. , межкультурная коммуникация английского языка.*

Introduction

This report is about “How to motivate children when teaching vocabulary. As teachers we know that good communication is vital for successful learning, so it is not surprising that this is a worry for English language teachers across the world. Communication skills help children to understand and explain the world around them, share their ideas and feelings and make friends. Good language skills enable a child to reason and learn. They also help to develop a sense of self and the feeling of belonging to a group or community.

The chosen article and time given

I chose the article “Keeping them interested” by Lucia Maffione and it was offered to discuss me. I agreed that 3 days would be enough to get ready for the discussion.

Key points of the article

This article suggested elicitation, personalization, peer teaching, games and role plays are just some strategies to motivate the learners when we are using vocabulary teaching activities. Whilst these techniques cannot force the students to learn new words, they can at least ensure the learners’ willing participation in the learning process.

How I felt about the article

So I find this article very useful and interesting. It was full of advice and activities that leads one to read it thoroughly in order to keep it in mind during the discussion. I agreed on the time and place of the discussion.

The following questions were introduced in order to analyze the article thoroughly:

1. Do I find the article interesting? Why?
2. What is elicitation, personalization, peer teaching, fun, different contexts?
3. How to motivate young learners to enrich their own vocabulary?
4. What activity do like most?

5. Are the activities suitable for a class of students with different learning styles?

6. What activity is more effective or more practical to you and your students?

Main issues raised in the discussion

While discussing the article I agreed on the following points:

- If we discover that there is a learner with speech and language difficulties in our class we might wonder how to help them to get the most from our lessons.
 - By understanding the different kinds of speech and language impairment and knowing some useful teaching strategies we can really make a difference to these learners and help them to experience enjoyable and successful learning.
 - Some learners have problems with the muscular movements needed to form words. They may have trouble producing certain sounds and simply leave them out, or substitute one sound for another. This can make them difficult to understand and result in delayed or unclear speech.
 - I also find it helpful to give students specific rules for how they are to talk to each other in group work - rules like 'everyone must share all their information' , 'everyone must speak equally', 'everyone is responsible for good group work', 'everyone must give reasons and explanations', 'everyone must ask for reasons and explanations' and so on. This method of explicit ground rules for group work has been very successful in British primary schools, where it has helped children learn to solve maths problems in groups - and researchers noted that not only did they solve the problems 'better', but the individual IQs of the children also went up! I'm not sure whether we are able to influence our students' IQs like this, but it certainly helped mixed nationality classes who appreciated having one set of rules that we all followed and were able to refer to.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, I want to tell you about my chosen task of discussion professional article very useful for us, because like this articles we can motivate children's knowledge by teaching vocabulary, grammar, writing, reading and etc. as a facilitator, I enjoyed and gained a lot of observing the process of discussing professional article.

In my opinion, to apply analyzing activities during group discussions gave a chance to students to feel free. They can think and have a talk with their own opinions.

The article is very useful it gave me good plans how can I organize my future lessons. I got information on setting and applying skills and encouraging learners to be participate actively.

References

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